

Assessment of Knowledge, Attitude and Practice of a Sample of a Mothers Attending Primary Health Care Centers Toward Febrile Convulsion in Children Under 5 Years Old in Baghdad, Al-Resafa (2018)

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Abstract

Background: Febrile convulsions are common in children under five years of age and often cause significant fear and anxiety among parents. Insufficient parental knowledge may lead to inappropriate management during convulsive episodes. **Objectives:** This study aimed to assess mothers' knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding febrile convulsions in children under five years of age and to identify the main sources of their information. **Methods:** A cross-sectional analytical study was conducted among 200 mothers attending six primary health care centers in Al-Rusafa, Baghdad, from 17 January to 20 June 2018. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire after a pilot study. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS software. Descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, and p-values were applied, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$. **Results:** Febrile convulsions were reported in 49 children, with males accounting for 76.5% of cases. Most mothers recognized fever as a risk factor for febrile convulsions (89.5% among mothers of affected children versus 83% among others). Awareness of the role of family history was also high (96.6% and 74.5%, respectively). Negative attitudes toward social stigma were common in both groups, while approximately one-fifth perceived febrile convulsions as life-threatening. Regarding practices, lowering body temperature was reported by 62.7% of mothers of affected children and 77.3% of those without affected children. Hospitals and primary health care centers were the main information sources for mothers of affected children, whereas relatives were the primary source for others. **Conclusion:** Family history and male sex were significant factors associated with febrile convulsions. Mothers demonstrated acceptable knowledge and attitudes but inadequate practices. Health facilities were the principal information sources, highlighting the importance of strengthening parental education on febrile convulsions.

Introduction

Febrile convulsion (FC) is the most common type of seizure in early childhood, affecting approximately 2–5% of children under five years of age, with peak incidence during the second year of life. It is typically associated with fever, and consensus guidelines define FC as a seizure occurring in the presence of an axillary temperature above 37.8 °C or a clinical history and

examination suggestive of fever-related seizures [1]. The diagnosis of febrile convulsion is primarily clinical and depends largely on parental descriptions of the seizure episode. Although the exact pathophysiology remains unclear, genetic predisposition is recognized as a significant contributing factor. Most febrile convulsions are benign and occur in association with minor viral infections; however, prompt medical

More Information

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evaluation is essential, particularly during the first seizure episode, to identify the underlying cause of fever and alleviate parental anxiety. Importantly, serious conditions such as pyogenic meningitis must be excluded through clinical assessment and, when indicated, lumbar puncture [2,3]. Despite its generally favorable prognosis, febrile convulsion is a highly distressing experience for families. Parents often fear long-term consequences such as recurrence, cognitive impairment, physical disability, and even death. Studies have reported that more than 80% of parents fear their child may die during the first convulsive episode. Nevertheless, febrile convulsion is not typically associated with adverse effects on intelligence or learning abilities. The risk of developing epilepsy following febrile convulsion is estimated at 2–7%, which is higher than the less than 1% risk observed in children without a history of febrile convulsions [2]. Parental lack of awareness and inadequate understanding of febrile convulsions often lead to inappropriate responses and mismanagement during seizure episodes. Adequate parental knowledge regarding the causes, clinical features, management, and prevention of febrile convulsions is therefore crucial. Although febrile convulsions are usually brief and self-limiting, appropriate first-aid measures can reduce potential complications such as head injury, oral trauma, and suffocation [4,5]. Accordingly, this study aimed to assess mothers’ knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding febrile convulsions in children under five years of age, including both mothers with and without affected children. Additionally, the study sought to identify the main sources of mothers’ information about febrile convulsions in both groups.

Method

A cross-sectional analytical study was conducted to assess mothers’ knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding febrile convulsions in children under five years of age. The study was carried out in six primary health care centers (PHCCs) in Al-Rusafa district, Baghdad, Iraq, over a six-month period from 17 January to 20 June 2018. The study population consisted of

mothers attending the selected PHCCs who had children younger than five years, including both mothers with a history of febrile convulsions in their children and those without such history. A total sample of 200 mothers was included in the study. The sample size was determined based on feasibility and attendance rates at the selected centers. Mothers who consented to participate were recruited using a convenient sampling technique. Data were collected using a structured, interviewer-administered questionnaire developed after reviewing relevant literature. The questionnaire consisted of four main sections: sociodemographic characteristics, knowledge about febrile convulsions, attitudes toward febrile convulsions, and practices related to the management of febrile convulsions. Additionally, mothers were asked about their sources of information regarding febrile convulsions. A pilot study was conducted to assess the clarity and validity of the questionnaire, and necessary modifications were made before the main data collection. Knowledge, attitude, and practice items were scored according to predefined criteria. Mothers’ levels of knowledge, attitude, and practice were categorized as adequate or inadequate based on their scores. Data were coded, entered, and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages, were used to summarize the data. Inferential statistical analysis was performed using the chi-square test to examine associations between variables, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$. Ethical approval was obtained from the relevant health authorities. Verbal informed consent was secured from all participating mothers, and confidentiality of the collected data was ensured throughout the study.

Results

In Table 1 shows that the mothers that lived in core family were 32 (54.2%) for those have children with FC compared to 27 (45.8%) living in extended family. Mean of family size were (7.3,7.0) for mothers had FC child or had not respectively.

Table 1: Family Properties Part 1(Socio-Demographic)

Family properties		Have a child with FC				P value
		Yes (n=59)		No (n=141)		
		No	%	No	%	
Family type	core	32	54.2	72	51.1	0.682
	extended	27	45.8	69	48.9	
Family size	3	2	3.4	11	7.8	0.0001*
	4	7	11.9	34	24.1	
	5	11	18.6	18	12.8	
	6	8	13.6	23	16.3	
	7	8	13.6	20	14.2	
	8	4	6.8	5	3.5	

	9	8	13.6	-	-	
	=>10	11	18.6	30	21.3	
	Mean± SD (Range)	7.3±2.9 (3-15)		7.0±4.5 (3-31)		
*Significant difference between proportions using Pearson Chi-square test ≤ 0.05 level.						

In **Table 2** Regarding the mothers and father characteristics: the mean of the age of mothers had FC child was (30.3) with standard deviation (6.6), and the mean was (28.7) with standard deviation (5.5) for those had not. The education level for mothers with FC was 24 (40.7%) for primary school while the higher education mothers 45(31.9%) had the highest score for

those without FC child. Furthermore, 55 (93.2%) were a housewives and 4(6.8%) were government employee for mothers with FC child. Regarding the mean of fathers age was (34.7) and standard deviation of (7) for those with FC child, primary school level was reported in 20 (33.9%), with majority were with private work 44 (74.6%).

Table 2: Family Properties Part 2

Family properties		Have a child with FC				P value
		Yes (n=59)		No (n=141)		
		No	%	No	%	
Age of the mother (years)	<20	-	-	7	5.0	0.055
	20---29	35	59.3	69	48.9	
	30---39	18	30.5	59	41.8	
	40---49	6	10.2	6	4.3	
	Mean±SD (Range)	30.3±6.6 (20-49)		28.7±5.5 (17-41)		
Mother education	Illiterate	2	3.4	6	4.3	0.001*
	Read & Write	6	10.2	2	1.4	
	Primary	24	40.7	37	26.2	
	Secondary	15	25.4	36	25.5	
	College/Institute	7	11.9	15	10.6	
	Higher education	5	8.5	45	31.9	
Mother job	Housewife	55	93.2	112	79.4	0.034*
	Gov. employee	4	6.8	19	13.5	
	Others(private work)	-	-	10	7.1	
Age of the father (years)	<30	8	13.6	39	27.7	0.021*
	30---39	36	61.0	69	48.9	
	40---49	9	15.3	29	20.6	
	=>50	6	10.2	4	2.8	
	Mean± SD (Range)	34.7±7.0 (24-51)		34.4±7.3 (21-50)		
Father education	Illiterate	-	-	2	1.4	0.0001*
	Read & Write	6	10.2	2	1.4	
	Primary	20	33.9	17	12.1	
	Secondary	14	23.7	34	24.1	
	College/Institute	5	8.5	17	12.1	
	Higher education	14	23.7	69	48.9	
Fathers job	Gov. employee	15	25.4	56	39.7	0.027*
	Private work	44	74.6	79	56.0	
	Not working	-	-	6	4.3	
*Significant difference between proportions using Pearson Chi-square test ≤ 0.05 level.						

In **Table 3** Parental Consanguinity were found in 43 (72.9%) for mothers had child with FC. First degree

family history with FC were 29 (49.2%), while those with second degree family history of FC were 10 (16.9%).

Table 3: Family Properties Part 3

Family properties		Have a child with FC				P value
		Yes (n=59)		No (n=141)		
		No	%	No	%	
Parental consanguinity	Yes	43	72.9	53	37.6	0.0001*
	No	16	27.1	88	62.4	
Family history of FC	First degree	29	49.2	-	-	-
	Second degree	10	16.9	-	-	
	NO	20	33.9			

*Significant difference between proportions using Pearson Chi-square test ≤ 0.05 level.

The Table 4 shows FC number was reported in mothers had one child were 46 (80.7%) and for mothers with two children having FC were 11 (19.3%). The mean age of child was (2.1) with standard deviation (0.9), the

majority of children were male 52 (76.5%), and the majority of time of convulsion to occur was one time 37(54.4%) and two time recurrence of convulsion occur in 21 (30.9%) of them.

Table 4: Characteristic of Child with FC

Have a child with febrile convulsion (n=59)		No	%
Number of children with FC	1	46	80.7
	2	11	19.3
Child age (years) (n=68)	<1	4	5.9
	1---	19	27.9
	2---	26	38.2
	3---	14	20.6
	4---	3	4.4
	5---	2	2.9
	Mean±SD (Range)	2.1±0.9 (9M-5Y)	
Child gender (n=68)	Male	52	76.5
	Female	16	23.5
Recurrences of convulsion (n=68)	once	37	54.4
	twice	21	30.9
	Three times	4	5.9
	Four times	6	8.8

The highest correct response was in lowering the child body temperature (62.7% in mothers had child with FC, 77.3% in mothers had child without FC). Table 5 shows that knowledge score divided into three

categories (poor, acceptable/fair, good) in response to 12 questions, the majority of mothers had acceptable/fair either the mothers had FC child or had not.

Table 5: Mother's Knowledge Score

Knowledge Score (Q=12)	FC		No		
Poor	8	13.6	42	29.8	0.047*
Acceptable/Fair	31	52.5	56	39.7	
Good	20	33.9	43	30.5	
Total	59	100%	141	100%	

In Table 6 the attitude score divided into three categories (poor, fair/acceptable, good) in response to 10 question majority of mother's response were

fair/acceptable in both mothers with child had FC or not.

Table 6: Mother’s Attitude Score

Attitude Score (Q=10)	FC		No		
Poor	-	-	3	2.1	0.002*
Acceptable/Fair	52	88.1	134	95.0	
Good	7	11.9	4	2.8	
Total	59	100%	141	100%	

In Table 7 shows the practice score divided into three categories (poor, fair/acceptable, good) in response to 16 question majority of mothers have child with FC

response were poor and the mothers having child without FC the response is acceptable/fair.

Table 7: Mothers Practice Score

Practice Score (Q=16)					
Poor	47	79.7	50	35.5	0.0001*
Acceptable/Fair	12	20.3	67	47.5	
Good	-	-	24	17.0	
Total	59	100%	141	100%	

In Table 8 shows comparison of different source of information in mothers having child with FC the majority were the hospital and PHCC as a source, in the

mothers having child without FC the majority was from relatives as a source of information.

Table 8: Mothers Source of Information’s

The main source of information about FC	Have a child with FC				P value
	Yes (n=59)		No (n=141)		
	No	%	No	%	
Hospital/PHCC	37	62.7	39	27.7	0.0001*
Relatives	22	37.3	50	35.5	
Neighbors	-	-	34	24.1	
Social media/Internet	-	-	2	1.4	
Others	-	-	16	11.3	

Discussion

Febrile convulsions (FC) represent the most common seizure disorder in early childhood and are generally benign with favorable neurodevelopmental outcomes [4]. Despite their relatively good prognosis, FC episodes are often perceived as frightening and emotionally traumatic by parents, leading to anxiety and inappropriate responses during seizures [6]. Adequate parental knowledge, positive attitudes, and appropriate practices are therefore essential to reduce complications and improve the management of febrile convulsions.

In the present study, the mean age of children with febrile convulsions was 2.1 years, which is comparable to findings from Sudan (1.86 years) and Iran (1.5 years) [7,8]. This confirms that FC most frequently occurs in early childhood, particularly during the second year of life. Male predominance was observed (76.5%), consistent with previous studies reporting higher incidence among males [5,8].

The mean age of mothers (30.3 years) was similar to that reported in Iranian studies [8]. Most mothers were

housewives, which aligns with findings from Mohammed et al. [5]. A high rate of parental consanguinity (72.9%) and first-degree family history of FC (49.2%) was observed, supporting the role of genetic factors in FC susceptibility. This prevalence was higher than that reported in Sudan, possibly reflecting cultural practices of consanguineous marriage in Iraq [7]. Genetic mechanisms involving sodium and gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) channel mutations have been implicated in febrile seizures [4].

The study revealed that many mothers believed high fever inevitably leads to convulsions, which is a misconception also reported in other studies [9]. However, a substantial proportion of mothers correctly differentiated FC from epilepsy, indicating an acceptable level of knowledge. This finding was comparable to Graves RC et al. but higher than that reported by Kayserili et al. [9,10].

Awareness of family history as a risk factor was high among mothers, consistent with the genetic basis of FC [6]. Nevertheless, misconceptions regarding the routine use of anticonvulsants, diagnostic

investigations (EEG, CT, LP), and immunization were observed. These findings are consistent with earlier studies showing that unnecessary investigations and long-term anticonvulsant therapy are not recommended in simple febrile convulsions due to limited benefits and potential adverse effects [2,11].

Mothers in both groups demonstrated generally fair attitudes toward FC, with no significant differences between those with and without affected children. Most mothers did not perceive FC as socially shameful, consistent with findings from previous studies [5,10]. However, a proportion of mothers believed that FC could cause brain damage or death, reflecting persistent anxiety and misunderstanding of prognosis. Evidence from longitudinal studies indicates that FC is not associated with increased mortality or cognitive impairment, and children with FC do not differ in intelligence from their peers or siblings [4].

The practice component revealed the lowest scores among the KAP domains, consistent with findings from other studies [5,6]. Many mothers lacked thermometers, were unfamiliar with proper temperature measurement, and did not apply appropriate first-aid measures during seizures. Incorrect practices such as shaking the child, forcefully opening the mouth, or using traditional remedies were also reported, similar to observations in Turkey, Taiwan, and India [10,12,13]. These harmful practices highlight the gap between knowledge and actual behavior.

Conversely, mothers without a history of FC in their children demonstrated relatively better practices, possibly due to higher educational levels and reduced emotional stress during seizures.

Hospitals and primary health care centers were the primary sources of information for mothers of affected children, whereas relatives were the main source for mothers without affected children. This pattern has been reported in previous studies [5,14,15]. The reliance on informal sources raises concerns about the accuracy of transmitted information and underscores the need for structured health education programs. Overall, this study demonstrates that mothers possess acceptable knowledge and attitudes toward febrile convulsions but inadequate practical skills. Strengthening parental education through health care institutions is crucial to improve seizure management and reduce harmful practices.

Conclusion

Mothers of children with febrile convulsions (FC) were slightly older than those without affected children, and most mothers were housewives with relatively low educational levels. A high proportion of FC cases occurred in males, and nearly half of affected children had a positive first-degree family history, suggesting a genetic influence. Mothers of children with FC showed

inadequate knowledge and attitudes toward febrile convulsions, with persistent concerns about their children's health and misconceptions about prognosis. Practical management of FC was suboptimal in both groups, with practice scores being lower than knowledge and attitude levels in the KAP assessment. Hospitals and primary health care centers were the main information sources for mothers of affected children, whereas relatives were the primary source for mothers without FC history.

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